

THE IMPACTS OF CLASS SIZE ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF FACEBOOK PEER ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

Online peer assessment on Facebook has been proved to be a successful technological tool for supporting English writing classes thanks to its effectiveness to students' learning performance and learning satisfaction and processes (Chang & Chen, 2009; Lu & Bol, 2007; Nurlia, 2014; Shih, 2010; van Gennip, Segers & Tillema, 2010; Xie, Ke & Sharma, 2008; Xiao & Lucking, 2008; van Zundert, Sluijsmans & van Merrienboer, 2010; Wichadee, 2013). The implementation of peer assessment tends to be less likely to achieve fruitful outcomes with classes of large size because of certain challenges confronted by both teachers and students (Agaron, 2003; Hron & Friedrich, 2003; Qiu, Hewitt, & Brett, 2012). In English language teaching, however, few studies investigate possible impacts of class size on the effectiveness of Facebook peer assessment in English writing classes. Thus, this gap is explored in the current study. In particular, the study employs a qualitative case study approach and utilizes data from the survey with 107 students and the interviews with two English lecturers of three classes of English essay writing for English-as-a-medium-of-instruction (EMI) classes. The results reveal there are certain impacts of class size on the implementation of Facebook peer feedback in EMI classes in terms of its merits and drawbacks. Based on the findings, possible recommendations are then proposed for further successful implementation of online peer assessment on students' Facebook groups especially to large classes.

Key words: Class size, English writing class, Facebook peer assessment

1 INTRODUCTION

The internet technology (IT) has widely been adopted in the field of education thanks to its positive impacts on not only enhancing instructors' professional development but also promoting learners' knowledge and skill competence (Duran, Brunvand, Fossum, 2009; Kilimci, 2010; Liu & Lee, 2013). As one of the most widely used forms in second language teaching and learning, online peer assessment has been recently highly valued with various forms such as peer feedback using blogs, peer feedback on forum, or peer feedback on Facebook (Dippold, 2009; Kung, 2018; Noytim, 2010; Nurlia, 2014; Phuong, 2012; Shih, 2011; Wang, 2007; Wichadee, 2013). In particular, online peer assessment on Facebook has been proved to be a successful technological tool for supporting English writing classes thanks to its effectiveness to students' achievement in learning outcome (Alotumi, 2015; Chen (2016); Lu & Bol, 2007; Nurlia, 2014; Shih, 2010; Suthiwartnarueput & Wasanasomsithi, (2012); Wichadee, 2013). In other words, the fruitful

outcomes of this form of assessment has been revealed as promoting students' motivation, participation, and collaboration among peers (Wichadee, 2013). Sharing the same concern, Nurlia (2014) believes that students' learning could significantly be enhanced via Face peer assessment resulting from their evaluating and observing their peers' writing. Similar effects of Facebook peer feedback were found to enhance students' learning in terms of not only creating a meaningful learning environment but also offering students to get feedback in a more constructive and less burdensome way (Alotumi, 2015; Shil, 2010).

Despite such the recognized effects of online peer assessment, its implementation is less likely to fully achieve the outcomes because of certain challenges with large class size confronted by both teachers and students. It is due to the fact that online peer assessment tends to share several features of online learning settings in which asynchronous online discussions need to be considerately organized to engage students in discourses (Qiu, Hewitt, & Brett, 2012). The authors further clarify another challenge of online peer assessment in terms of overloaded information from the online settings. This may lead to students' anxiety, prevent shy students from interaction, and cause their loss of personalization and sense of individuality. A further significant inhibiting factor related to collaborative learning in online peer assessment is large class size since the number of students in the virtual classes are required to establish their social presence and contribute greater interactivity (Agaron, 2003; Hron & Friedrich, 2003). Therefore, the impacts of class size will be able to happen to Facebook peer feedback. However, there have been few studies investigating possible impacts of class size on the Facebook peer assessment. To fill such gap, the current study was aimed to explore the extent to which class size affects the online peer feedback on Facebook in English writing class. The following research questions are addressed:

To what extent has class size affected students' perceptions of online peer feedback on Facebook?

What has teachers perceived the impacts of class size on the effectiveness of online peer feedback on Facebook?

In general, as the investigation into the impacts of class size on online feedback on Facebook is disclosed, it is believed to be greatly significant in contributing to the current literatures of online peer feedback implications to English language teaching and learning.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Impacts of class size on online learning

Although extant studies have investigated the implementation of online learning, few studies explored the impacts of class size on this form of learning. The implications of class size and online learning, however, have been still concerned in several studies (Aragon, 2003; Bender, 2003; Drago & Peltier, 2004; Hewitt & Brett 2007; Lipponen & Lallimo 2004; Roberts & Hopewell, 2003; Rovai, 2002). One significant study by Dragon and Peltier (2004) exploring the predictive power of class size on the effectiveness of online MBA courses of a university in

Midwestern United States showed that there was no significant relationship found between these two variables. However, the participants of this online course proposed the use of small groups of thirteen to fifteen students for their better collaborative discussions. Hewitt and Brett (2007) also claim that larger classes provide individual students with a wider range of ideas and perspectives than they would experience otherwise. However, students in larger classes must process more information, so the time that a teacher spends with individual learners may be reduced. With more explicit explanation, Tomei (2006, p.531) argues that the excess effectiveness of online teaching cannot be achieved, resulting from the large class size which is closely connected to the expense of effective instructional and faculty oversubscription. Sharing the same concern, some research has revealed certain problems related to large class size such as information being overloaded (Hewitt & Brett 2007; Lipponen & Lallimo 2004), and teachers' being overwhelmed (Bender, 2003). This may lead to the increase in students' anxiety, which can interfere participants' attention ability in online learning.

To confront with such challenges of class size, various views have been shared for optimal sizes for online learning settings. Based on online teaching experience, both Aragon (2003) and Bi (2000) shared the same suggestion to the number of approximately 30 students as an ideal number to optimize and allow students for effective feedback. However, Roberts and Hopewell (2003) suggested the size of the class to 20 students so as to provide e-class participants with more workable loads and this size can be easily managed by teachers to avoid overwhelming or minimizing their effectiveness. Focusing on the small class size for its effectiveness, however, Rovai (2002) suggests that the number of students in online classes should be from 8 to 10 students to guarantee effective online engagement and interactions.

In general, despite the fact that there can be various significant factors to be considered for the optimal online learning settings, class size has still played a very crucial role in maximizing the achievable outcomes as well as minimizing potential challenges in the virtual teaching and learning process such as teachers' motivation, students' participation and discussion.

2.2 Impacts of class size on peer assessment

Different studies have been shared about the impacts of class size on peer assessment, but their arguments for the positive effects of class size on such form of assessment seem to be rather blurred. Despite the fact that peer assessment can be used as a better solution of maintaining the quality of assessment and feedback in large groups of students as students are encouraged to involve in their learning process (Ballantyne, Hughes, & Mylonas; 2002; Pond, Ul-Haq, & Wade, 1995), it seems not to be agreed by later views. As Billington, (1997) argues, class sizes and academic staff workloads have risen dramatically, which requires teachers a huge amount of time and effort to evaluate the performance of students. This leads them to being arduous and overwhelmed in larger classes. Sharing the same concern, Gibbs, Lucas, & Spouse (1997) claim that larger classes bring about less positive effects for students' learning since their teachers tend to give less detailed or frequent feedback on assessment tasks and less tutorial support to every student.

Regarding teachers' responsibility for this form of assessment and class size impacts, a study by Ballantyne, Hughes, and Mylonas (2002) investigated the development of peer assessment procedures for use in large classes, using a cyclical process of action, reflection and refined action. The development of procedures was discussed in relation to assessment tasks, assessment criteria, anonymity, procedural guidelines, distribution systems, marking procedures and tutor remarking. The findings revealed several inhibiting factors related to peer assessment listed by the students' participants such as time consuming, difficulty reaching group consensus, lack of assessment experience, lack of tutor moderation, and unclear criteria and instruction. Of these factors, lack of tutor moderation has been linked to teachers dealing with many students' work. However, the authors claim that although there are specific challenges related to the use of peer assessment in large classes, such challenges seemed to be outweighed by the fruitful outcomes achieved by students in terms of increasing students' interest, engaging them in learning from their peers' work, and developing their future employment skills.

Sharing the same concern, a study by Hanrahan and Isaacs (2001) investigating students' experiences with self and peer assessment also indicated that time commitment was closely linked to peer assessment, so staff workload was implied in terms of the fact that the more students in classes, the more work teachers should do with the process of peer assessment. This was explicitly explained that teachers were required to not only logically operate the procedure of this form of assessment but also ensure well tracking the process.

It is generally concluded that the implementation of peer assessment seems to be a promising measure for large classes to optimize students' learning engagement, but major challenging factors needed to be considered are time consumption and instructional workload.

2.3 Facebook feedback in English writing classes

Facebook feedback as a mean of learning English has been investigated in various studies with university to college students in both EFL and ESL classrooms. Related to the context of the current study, this part mainly focuses on the findings of those studies investigating Facebook peer feedback in English writing class. In particular, Suthiwartnarueput and Wasanasomsithi (2012) conducted an experimental study to investigate the effects of peer feedback on Facebook on students' grammar and writing ability. The participants of the study included 83 first-year undergraduate students at a University in Nakhon Pathom province, Thailand. They were between 18 and 22 years old. They were considered as low-intermediate EFL students and were placed in the English level 1 course because their Ordinary National Education Testing score in the English section was less than 45 points. In the first stage of the study, the pre-test was given to find out the students' background knowledge in English Grammar and writing competence. During the intervention, the students were allowed to send messages, post their pieces of writing or chat about English Grammar and difficulties in writing. At the end of the research, a post-test was given to them with the aim of finding out to what extent the students' English grammatical and writing competence improved. The findings indicated that the students used grammatical

structures more skillfully and made significant improvement in writing after the treatment. Besides the statistically significant difference of the mean scores between the pre-test and post-test, it was found that the students wrote more meaningful content in a better organized paragraph in the post-test than they did in the pre-test. It is concluded that the student participants in this study revealed their positive attitudes to using Facebook in their class as this social network offered them opportunities to engage in discussions with their teachers and other peers so as to enhance their English grammar and writing skill.

Other experimental studies by Shih (2011), Wichadee (2013), Nurlia (2014) and Alotumi (2015) share the same focus on exploring the effects of peer feedback on students' writing performance. The results of the studies demonstrated positive outcomes achieved by the students in terms of significantly improving their writing ability and gaining their optimistic attitudes towards the use of Facebook for peer feedback. In Shih's (2011) experimental study, the effect of integrating Facebook and peer assessment with college English writing class instruction through a blended teaching approach was examined. The study was conducted in eighteen weeks in which one third of a semester was used for face-to-face learning and during two-thirds of a semester, the combination of Facebook, peer assessment, and classroom instruction was implemented. Twenty-three first-year students (18 females and 5 males) majoring in English at a technological university in Taiwan participated in the study. The participants were divided into three categories (high score = 90 points and above, medium score = 70-89 points, and low score = 70 points and below) according to their English subject scores on the National College Entrance Examination in 2010. There were 8 students in the high-score group, 7 students in the medium-score group, and 8 students in the low-score group. Both quantitative and qualitative approaches were employed in the study. The research instruments included pre-test and post-test of English writing skills, a self-developed survey questionnaire, and in-depth interviews. The findings suggested that incorporating peer assessment using Facebook in learning English writing can be interesting and effective for college-level English writing classes. Students can improve their English writing skills and knowledge not only from the in-class instruction but also from cooperative learning. This Facebook integrated instruction can significantly enhance students' interest and motivation in learning writing.

In the study by Wichadee (2013), Facebook peer feedback was explored in relation to its impacts on students' writing performance. Particularly, the study was aimed to offer the insight into how faculty staff could use this social networking to facilitate student learning and how much it can improve student writing performance. The participants were 30 undergraduate students who joined a Facebook group to give and receive feedback of their writing papers of the fundamental English course of one-semester study. Data were collected from the first and final drafts of their writing assignments, written peer comments, a questionnaire and an interview. The results revealed that the peer comments and revisions to the drafts reflected the significantly positive outcomes of feedback on Facebook with regard to improving participants' revised drafts.

However, the findings also indicated certain negative feedback shared by few student participants such as wasting time and feeling uncomfortable to post their work on Facebook.

With the same focus on Facebook peer feedback, the quasi-experimental study by Nurlia (2014) was to determine the effect of online peer feedback through Closed Group Facebook on the students' writing achievement. The research used quasi-experimental, non-randomized control group, pre and post-test design and analysis of covariance to analyse data. The findings revealed that participants found this strategy beneficial and effective for their writing skill development in terms of helping them to be active learners, improving their confidence, improving their own writing by reading and commenting their peers' writing. One major challenge discussed in the study was that online peer feedback seemed less effective in helping the students revise their language used and mechanics.

Another experimental study conducted by Alotumi (2015) investigated Yemeni EFL students' perceptions, attitudes and challenges on integrating Facebook Interaction (FBI) to improve their essay writing. The participants consisted of fifty Yemeni higher-intermediate EFL learners (28 males and 22 females) participated in this study, and they were in three different classes. In this study, the researcher created three FB groups and the respondents were required to take part in Facebook interaction for the purpose of an essay writing pre-task. In the Facebook groups, the teacher researcher posted an essay topic and each time there was an essay task. This was aimed to enrich students with their views, images, videos, or relevant hypermedia of their own choice. The total number of the writing sessions was six, and each writing session lasted two hours. Students were then asked to complete an online survey at the end. The data were collected from an online questionnaire with 17 closed-ended questions and three open-ended ones, which was used to measure students' perceptions, attitudes and challenges. The findings indicated the utilisation of Facebook interaction in writing pre-tasks received more positive than negative feedback from the respondents. The former included Facebook interaction helping students effectively in becoming familiar with the writing topics, forming better thought, brainstorming and mind-mapping, reducing spelling errors, as well as acquiring and practising new vocabulary. However, certain issues related the latter feedback were typing and time pressure.

It can be seen that the aforementioned studies not only share the same concern about the relationships between Facebook peer feedback and students' writing skill development but also reveal more positive than negative perceptions from the participants. However, despite various challenging factors influencing the implementation of online feedback on Facebook being revealed, the issues related to class size have not been particularly discussed. As a consequence, seeking potential impacts of class size on Facebook peer feedback is hoped as greatly significant contribution to the current literature of this issue.

3 THE STUDY

3.1 Participants

Participants of the current study includes 107 EFL students (58 males and 49 females, average age of 18.5) from 3 writing classes in an English foundation program to prepare for them for future EMI courses. Class 1 and 2 are large classes with 40 and 42 students respectively. Class 3 is a small class with 25 students. At the time of the study, all these student participants had had seven years of learning English at secondary school and high school. However, the placement test at the beginning of the program revealed that their English entrance level is only A1 or above according to the European Common Framework of Reference for Foreign Language (CEFR).

In addition, two writing teachers teaching these three classes were invited to participate in an interview on their implementation of Facebook peer feedback. Both participants are female and had 18 years of teaching experience. Teacher 1 taught Class 1 of 40 students while Teacher 2 taught Class 2 and 3 with 42 and 25 students respectively. Both teachers shared their ideas about the impact of large classes on their implementation of online peer feedback on Facebook, whereas Teacher 2 compared and contrasted the impact of both types of class size on the effectiveness of her intervention.

3.2 The procedure

During the fifteen-week writing course, 107 students in the three classes learned how to write three different kinds of English essays namely opinion, causes and effects, and problems and solution. Students were instructed how to write these essays in class and required to write their essays at home. Each class had a closed group on Facebook. Since every student had a Facebook account, there was no problem adding them to the group.

The students were randomly assigned to groups of four or five. Class 1 consisted of 10 groups of four, Class 2 with 8 groups of four and 2 groups of five, Class 3 with 5 groups of four and 1 group of five. These groups were stable during the course. After the instruction of each essay, students were given 5 topics and members in each groups negotiated to choose a topic to write as long as members in the same group did not write the same topic.

After a student finished his essay, he uploaded it on the class close group and invited his group members to read and give feedback on it by tagging their names on his post. Students were required to give feedback on four important features of the essay including task fulfillment, organization, vocabulary, and grammar. In addition, students can also help one another recognize the errors in these texts. Students of the whole class can see all the posts and comments of all the groups and it can be seen from Facebook the number of people who have read each text.

After receiving feedback and comments from their group members, the student participants revised the essays to write their second drafts. These drafts were posted in the comment section of the first draft. The teacher in each class was then tagged by the students to give further

comments. Some students were given the third chance to rewrite their essays if the teacher thought that it was necessary. Students' final drafts were then printed and sent to the teachers for grading.

After 15 weeks of the writing courses and Facebook peer feedback intervention, the teachers sent a questionnaire on Google Forms to students and asked them to answer the questionnaire. Meanwhile, the teacher participants were invited to individual interviews.

3.3 The questionnaire

A brief questionnaire was designed to explore students' perceptions toward the benefits and challenges of Facebook peer feedback. The questionnaire consists of three open-ended questions. Question 1 and 2 ask students to list at least two advantages and two disadvantages of online peer feedback on Facebook. Question 3 asks if they wanted to do online peer feedback on Facebook in their coming writing course and why? These open-ended questions are helpful to shed some light on what the participants actually perceive about the intervention and avoid possible bias of Likert-scale questionnaire.

3.4 The interviews

The two teachers were interviewed individually for about 25 minutes each. The questions explored the benefits and challenges of online peer feedback on Facebook and the teachers' ideas about whether class size has an impact on their intervention.

3.5 Data collection and analysis

Since the purpose of the current study is comparing the impact of class size on online peer feedback on Facebook, only the benefits and challenges posed by more than 20% of the students in each class are listed and analyzed in this paper. Students did not have the exact same words in their answers, so their answers were grouped according to the meaning they expressed. For example, "*learning from peer's writing*", "*learning vocabulary and grammar structures from friends' texts*", "*I can learn new vocabulary from my friends*", "*I can learn a lot from my friends' essays*" were listed in the same umbrella item "*With Facebook online peer feedback, I can learn many things from peers' writing texts. For example, I can learn interesting ideas, new vocabulary and good sentence structures*".

4 THE FINDINGS

4.1 The impact of class size on students' perceptions of online peer feedback on Facebook

The study results reveal eleven main benefits that online peer feedback on Facebook offered the participants (see Table 1). Among these benefits, only Item 2, Item 5 and Item 11 received different proportion of responses from large classes (Class 1 and 2) as compared to the small class (Class 3). More specifically, many more students from Class 3 perceived that it is fast to give and receive feedback on Facebook (50% of responses as compared to 24% and 26%). That

can be because students from the small class could find their peers' posts more easily with the timeline default on Facebook. Meanwhile, because there were more students meaning more posts on the Facebook group of large classes, it was hard for the students to identify their peers' texts.

Table 1: Students' perception of the benefits of online peer feedback on Facebook

Benefits	Number of responses	% from Class 1	% from Class 2	% from Class 3
1. Online peer feedback on Facebook is convenient.	45	35%	33%	32%
2. It is fast to give and receive feedback on Facebook.	43	24%	26%	50%
3. Facebook provides me with the opportunities for exchanging ideas and comments spontaneously.	43	26%	28%	48%
4. With Facebook online peer feedback, I can write and submit the text from anywhere as long as I have internet access.	42	35%	33%	32%
5. With Facebook online peer feedback, I can learn many things from peers' writing texts. For example, I can learn interesting ideas, new vocabulary and good sentence structures.	39	37%	38%	25%
6. With Facebook online peer feedback, we can help each other discover and correct writing mistakes or errors.	39	35%	33%	32%
7. With Facebook online peer feedback, we save a lot of time meeting face-to-face with peers and the teacher.	39	35%	33%	32%
8. With Facebook online peer feedback, it is easy to recall and revise the text	38	34%	34%	32%
9. With Facebook online peer feedback, I can correct my own mistakes and errors thanks to friends' comments	38	34%	34%	32%
10. The activity of online peer feedback on Facebook is simple and easy to use because I am used to the Facebook interface.	28	34%	34%	32%
11. With Facebook online peer feedback, it is easy to access teacher and friends' comments	28	26%	28%	48%

For Item 5, more students from the large classes claimed that they can learn a lot from their peers' writing. This is logical because students in the large classes were exposed to more writing texts as compared to their friends in the small class.

Regarding Item 11, nearly half of responses were from students in the small class while the two large classes occupied only a quarter of responses each. Similar reasoning in Item 2 can be applicable here. A small class means fewer texts and fewer post on the class Facebook. Consequently, the students in this class can access their teacher and friends much more easily.

For the other eight items, there were no big differences between the large classes and small classes. This may be because these are general benefits of peer feedback that each individual student can receive.

Regarding the challenges of online peer feedback on Facebook, 5 major factors have been found among the three classes (see Table 2).

Table 2: Students' perception of the challenges of online peer feedback on Facebook

Benefits	Number of responses	% from Class 1	% from Class 2	% from Class 3
1. It's hard to find the previously posted texts on Facebook.	32	44%	44%	12%
2. With Facebook online peer feedback, I have to access to the internet when working.	21	33%	33%	34%
3. Sometimes, it's hard to understand my friend's comment. It's may be more comprehensible when we give feedback face-to-face.	20	30%	38%	32%
4. Because we have a lot of time to write the texts at home, our texts may not reveal our real competence when we take the writing tests.	15	33%	33%	33%
5. Not all people are on Facebook frequently	14	35%	35%	30%

In general, students in the three classes share similar ideas about the challenges they encountered when applying online peer feedback on Facebook. Almost the same proportions from students of each class agree on the four challenges of internet access (Item 2), comprehensibility (Item 3), skepticism about whether they would write that well in the time-constraint exams (Item 4), and individual availability online (Item 5). The only different between the small class and the two large classes is that much more students from the large classes (44%) claimed that it was difficult

for them to find the previously posted texts on Facebook. This is comprehensible because more students in large classes mean more texts on the timeline of Facebook. It would take them more time to find the text they wanted because all the texts were arranged according not only to the time they were posted but also according to the time the comments were written.

In short, there were certain types of impacts of the class size on students' perceptions towards the benefits and challenges of online peer feedback on Facebook. Students from the larger classes learned more from their friends than those from the small class. On the other hand, students from the small classes could assess their friends' and teacher's comments much more easily and had fewer problems with the nature of timeline default on Facebook than those from the large classes.

4.2 Teachers' perceptions of the impact of class size on the effectiveness of online peer feedback on Facebook

Interviews with the teachers of the three classes revealed some similarities between the two teachers regarding the challenges of implementing online peer feedback on Facebook in large classes. Both teachers claimed that the work load they thought would decrease because students corrected each other errors was then replaced by the time and efforts they had to make to give comments on students' second drafts on Facebook. Teacher 1 claimed:

... The most noticeable problem is time consumption. This means that I need to spend time waiting for my learners' feedback and checking it for giving them constructive comments...

They also had difficulties searching for a specific students' texts and sometimes missed the texts by several students. To some extent, the first challenge is similar to what Bender (2003) argues about the feeling of being overwhelmed in large class size, even on online learning. Teacher 2 said:

... students usually wait until the deadline I set to post their texts. Therefore, I have only 1 or 2 days to read the essays of 39 students in my class...

In addition, both teachers said that it was harder for them to engage students in large classes to involve students in online peer feedback. They had to send more reminds to students in large classes to post their texts. Meanwhile, with the small class, Teacher 2 said that it was easier for her to ask students to work online. This kind of impact is in line with the findings by Gilbert and Dabbagh (2005). According to them, a major challenge in online learning setting is how to structure asynchronous online discussions in order to engage students in meaningful discourse.

Despite of these challenges, both teachers agreed that online peer feedback on Facebook was useful for their students. It is noticeable that both teachers agreed that students learned more from their large classes because there were more learning sources available. For example, Teacher 1 stated:

The most noticeable benefit is the chances to learn from one another. When one student posts their writing on their class Facebook group, all 39 other students can read their text. Facebook has an interesting function of telling users how many people in the group read the post (the writing text). I usually see from 30 to 38 students read each of the text posted and when the exam

came, all texts received reading from class members. When students read their friends' texts, they can learn new ideas, collocations and vocabulary.

Moreover, both teachers perceived that online peer feedback provided them with better opportunities for students' formative assessment. For example, Teacher 2 said:

By implementing this form of assessment, I can improve my teaching methods and help students to become more active, so my class atmosphere will be less boring. Also, I can save a lot of papers and keep my students' data longer. I also feel more active and closer to my students as I could often observe what my students were working with their writing activities.

However, she also agreed that she could do formative assessment better with her small classes than her large classes.

To sum up, class size has influenced the ways the teachers implemented online peer feedback on Facebook. In other words, the intervention showed to be more effective with a smaller group of students than with a larger one. This idea is corresponding with Roberts and Hopewell's (2003) suggestion of including only 20 students in online classes to allow for more "workable" loads to teachers.

5 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION

The study sought to explore the extent to which class size affects the online peer feedback on Facebook in English writing class with respect to (1) the impact of class size on students' perceptions of online peer feedback on Facebook, and (2) teachers' perceptions of the impact of class size on the effectiveness of online peer feedback on Facebook. Concerning the first issue, the findings showed that the class size considerably affected students' perceptions on Facebook peer feedback which provided students with both benefits and challenges. In particular, students from the larger classes learned more from their peers than those from the small class who received more ideas. In contrast, students from the small class could involve in the process of assessing their friends' and teachers' comments much more easily as well as facing few problems with the nature of timeline default on Facebook than those from the large classes. The findings, therefore, are in line with what Hewitt and Brett (2007) relate the class size to the information that students can achieve. Additionally, the number of students in the small class in the current study was similar to the ideal number of students for the effectiveness of online peer feedback on Facebook suggested by Roberts and Hopewell (2003). Regarding the challenges, the findings showed that the class size did not reflect the differences of students' perceptions towards challenges in large or small classes; however, the findings are in line with previous studies in terms of inhibiting factors resulted from students' lack of assessment leading unconstructive feedback.

Relating the second issue of teachers' perceptions of the impact of class size on the effectiveness of online peer feedback on Facebook, the findings indicated that the class size has considerably influenced the ways the teachers utilised Facebook peer feedback. Particularly, the teachers found it more effective to implement such form of feedback in a smaller class than a larger one. The

findings are in line with Roberts and Hopewell's (2003) suggestion of the ideal number of students in a class and Gilbert and Dabbagh's (2005) implication to how to structure asynchronous online discussions in order to engage students in meaningful discourse. Additionally, the findings further showed that teachers must be confronted with the work load for spending more time and efforts to give students' final feedback and searching their students' comments. This is corresponding with what Bender (2003) related to the feeling of being overwhelmed in large class size mentioned by Lipponen and Lallimo (2004).

Several implications can be withdrawn from the current study. Firstly, the size of classes should be reduced for the more effective Facebook peer feedback. Secondly, students are recommended to tag their teachers and their friends so as to get closer acquaintances with them. This will optimize the interactions between teachers and students and between students and students. Thirdly, teachers are recommended to share the best final papers of their students in Facebook's notes so as to help students of other classes learn from constructing well-structured ideas in those papers.

For further studies, several aspects should be considered. Firstly, it is recommended for the further research to focus on how to maximize the use the Facebook peer feedback in other skills of English language such as Listening, Speaking and Reading. Secondly, the current study was only conducted with three classes, so it is suggested for further studies to include more classes of different size. Finally, although the current study employed Facebook as a means of peer feedback, teachers' feedback was also included for giving feedback to the final drafts revised by the students basing on their peers' comments. Therefore, it is recommended for further studies to explore the comparison between peer feedback and teacher feedback on different online forms such as Facebook, blogs and forums.

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